

THE ANNE ARUNDEL COMMUNITY COLLEGE

Journal of Emerging Scholarship

VOLUME 5
MAY 2026

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Self-confidence and Mentorship in the Community
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Dear reader,

We are delighted to present the fifth annual volume of the *Anne Arundel Community College Journal of Emerging Scholarship* — a milestone that reflects five years of growing student curiosity, rigorous inquiry, and scholarly achievement at AACC.

In 2026, as technological advances, environmental challenges, and societal shifts continue to reshape our world at an unprecedented pace, the value of undergraduate research has never been clearer. Our student authors have tackled timely and timeless questions — exploring innovations in science and technology, examining pressing social and environmental issues, and contributing fresh perspectives across the humanities and beyond. Their work demonstrates that meaningful scholarship begins not in distant laboratories or elite institutions, but right here in our classrooms, libraries, and community.

What makes this journal possible is the remarkable collaboration between talented students and dedicated faculty mentors. Every manuscript has undergone a thoughtful review process, helping students develop essential skills in critical thinking, persistence, and professional communication that will serve them well whether they transfer to four-year institutions or enter the workforce.

We hope that readers — fellow students, faculty, staff, community members, and external scholars — will find inspiration in these pages. May the research presented here spark new questions, encourage future submissions, and affirm that every voice has the potential to contribute to the ever-growing body of knowledge.

Sincerely,

The 2025–2026 Editorial Board

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The Ethics Behind Trashed DNA and How it is Done

KEY WORDS

trashed DNA
forensic genetics
Fourth Amendment
genetic genealogy
CODIS
privacy rights
familial searching

FACULTY MENTOR

Darian Senn-Carter, Ed.D.
Director and Professor,
Homeland Security and Criminal
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ABSTRACT

This literature review examines the scientific foundations, investigative value, and ethical and legal risks of using “trashed” or abandoned DNA, biological material left on discarded items such as tissues, cigarette butts, and food waste in criminal investigations. Drawing on forensic science research, case examples, and legal scholarship, the review explains how discarded DNA can be collected, processed, and compared through methods such as STR profiling, CODIS searches, and, increasingly, genetic genealogy techniques. Trashed DNA has helped solve cold cases, identify perpetrators, and support post-conviction exonerations, demonstrating its potential to advance public safety and justice outcomes. However, the expanded use of discarded DNA also raises significant concerns about privacy, informed consent, and constitutional protections. Because abandoned property typically carries diminished expectations of privacy, law enforcement may obtain DNA from trash without a warrant, creating opportunities for misuse and mission creep beyond serious violent crime. Additional risks include the exposure of sensitive medical or familial information, increased surveillance of communities, and the implication of relatives through genealogical searching. The literature review argues that, while trashed DNA can be a powerful investigative tool, its continued growth without clear safeguards threatens civil liberties and public trust. It recommends establishing statutory standards for collection and use, limiting applications to serious offenses, strengthening oversight and transparency, and expanding

research on accuracy, bias, and Fourth Amendment implications to better balance investigative benefits with ethical boundaries.

INTRODUCTION

In 2013, NPR published an article by Heather Dewey-Hagborg. She is an artist and biohacker based in New York whose interest is art as research and critique of technology (*Heather Dewey-Hagborg | Bio*, n.d.). Heather has a PhD in Electronic Arts and is a founding member of the European Research Council project looking at the relationship between DNA, evidence, and digital technology (*Heather Dewey-Hagborg | Bio*, n.d.). This review argues that while DNA on trash presents powerful investigative benefits, its expansion without clear legal safeguards and ethical boundaries risks privacy violations and constitutional concerns. Therefore, stronger policy frameworks and research are needed to balance justice with civil liberties.

In the NPR article, Heather found herself thinking about items people often leave behind at crime scenes, and began collecting the samples (Squires, 2013). She extracts DNA from them, then she compares the code to known traits of the human face. Next, the sample is sent to a sequencing company, which sends back the nucleotides that make up DNA (Squires, 2013). Later, with a program she designed herself, the nucleotides get processed and the code gets turned into traits (Squires, 2013). She goes in and fills in the gaps and compares to a sketch artist to see the accuracy.

Often, she would be asked how accurate the process is. Unfortunately, since the samples are anonymous, she has no real way of knowing. When she used her own DNA however, the results were split 50/50 (Squires, 2013). Half of the people asked told her it looked exactly like her, but the others thought it was not a perfect replica (Squires, 2013). The program seems to be very subjective. When originally reading this article, I thought about

the ethical considerations and how this might be useful for the criminal justice system. This literature review examines how DNA evidence is used today and the ethical concerns of using DNA samples in criminal investigations collected from trash.

This is an important topic, using DNA from trash can help improve the criminal justice system. It can allow for people who have been wrongfully convicted to be exonerated, and it can help solve cold cases. If used properly, and ethically, it can improve solving criminal cases. There is not much research on this topic and its possible benefits and downsides.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientific & Technical Foundations

Deoxy-ribonucleic acid, also known as DNA, holds vital information that is crucial for forensic cases. Within our DNA building blocks, no two people are the same, except identical twins (Bhoyar et al., 2024). DNA is what makes every person different; it can help determine what we look like and who we are. Unfortunately, DNA's integrity poses a challenge after it degrades (Bhoyar et al., 2024). Denaturation is the process when weak non-covalent bonds within a DNA sample break. These bonds can be broken by higher temperatures, lower pH levels, or a solution made to denature the sample. DNA degradation is known as the “process of disrupting single strands by intensifying the conditions that cause denaturation” (Bhoyar et al., 2024). When the certain conditions that help advance denaturation are heightened, it is known as degradation.

DNA denaturation begins right after death, which allows DNA to be an indicator for time of death and useful in post-mortem interval estimation (Bhoyar et al., 2024). In sexual assault cases, there is often dried seminal fluid, which contains spermatozoa, found on the victim's clothing. This leaves behind DNA, which can show how long it has been since it was deposited (Bhoyar et al., 2024). Spermatozoa is important as it can help determine the

time that the crime occurred.

DNA denaturation can affect forensic anthropology. It can assist in looking at the age of skeletal remains, determining gender, and geographic origins. It can also help look at how heat affects DNA damage, and how to recover a degraded sample (Bhoyar et al., 2024). The process poses some challenges. There are environmental factors that affect the degradation rate. This can make it difficult to observe the PMI and sample age.

Additionally, fragmentation can occur, which can cause the strands of DNA to become small and more difficult to observe. Chemical agents, such as natural compounds, environmental pollutants, and industrial chemicals, can have an effect as well. This can lead to DNA degradation and can cause DNA strand breaks. A way of studying degradation is gel electrophoresis, which separates fragments based on size and mobility by using an electric field in an agarose or polyacrylamide gel (Lee et al., 2012). Another is single-cell electrophoresis or comet assay, which uses individual cells and immobilizes them in an agarose gel within a microscope slide, then placed under electrical charge (Bhoyar et al., 2024). Electrophoresis observes the way that DNA fragments move away from the nucleus, giving it a comet-like shape, and allowing for examination of the DNA fragments size (Bhoyar et al., 2024). These are just two ways that DNA degradation is measured.

DNA degradation is a useful tool with cases involving DNA samples (Bhoyar et al., 2024). It can be used to observe several types of DNA, like saliva. Saliva is typically found at crime scenes, especially sexual assault cases (Gosch et al., 2023). It is a very common type of DNA evidence to collect. Identifying body fluids like saliva is a common aspect in forensic casework.

When using saliva, there should be careful planning that accounts for the challenges (Xu et al., 2023). Samples from saliva may contain very little usable human transcripts, meaning the identification of biomarkers might be unusable (Xu et al., 2023).

Xu et al (2023) recommend more research on how to protect the samples.

DNA use in forensics can include exoneration of innocent suspects, identification of victims, and reversal of wrongful convictions. In 2020, the Innocence Project reported having over 300 exonerations using DNA (Innocence Project, 2024). It is important for DNA to help those who have been wrongfully convicted. DNA degradation can help point out crime timelines and show insights into the post-mortem interval (Bhoyar et al., 2024). Post-mortem intervals, or the time since death, show many changes in the body, like rigor mortis, and enzyme functions. These changes are studied during investigations. Even with many changes to study, post-mortem interval (PMI) still has its limitations (Bhoyar et al., 2024). It is not a perfect process to observe.

Advances in Forensic Methodologies

Bones are an example of DNA used to solve criminal cases. Zooarchaeology is the combination field of the study of animals and study of human culture (*Zooarchaeology*, n.d.). Zoo archaeologists look at how people have interacted with animals in both the past and present (*Zooarchaeology*, n.d.). This field helps show how humans and animals have evolved and helped each other. This discipline was used with mass spectrometry and ancient DNA methods to observe a piece of biological evidence from a 20-year-old case (Xu et al., 2023). Zooarchaeology, used with current methods like mass spectrometry, have been used to look at evidence.

After analyzing the sample of a two decades old cold case, there was one identified human bone fragment (Xu et al., 2023). When testing, the sample failed the STR analysis. STR analysis tests for “short tandem repeats” (*National Institute of Justice*, n.d.). The test is based on how likely two people have the same number of repeated sequences (*National Institute of Justice*, n.d.). A myriad

of the human genome is very similar, around 99.9 percent. Short tandem repeats are sections of the human genome where the number of nucleotides differ greatly (NIST, 2023). There are portions of DNA that are different sizes based on the person. This can help identify individuals. The STR analysis on the bone fragments failed, which was credited to the possibility of the high level of degradation of DNA molecules (Xu et al., 2023). Researchers then took the bone fragments and applied strict ancient DNA protocols during all parts.

Sanger sequencing, a method for determining sequences of small regions of a genome, was performed (Van Campen, n.d.). Due to its 99% accuracy, it is considered the “gold standard” for DNA identification (Xu et al., 2023). After using primers to amplify the DNA, and completed Sanger sequencing, the sample was analyzed, and were able to identify the remains as a little boy. DNA evidence can be used to look at cold case samples for identification purposes (Xu et al., 2023). It can help identify missing persons or suspects for cases that have remained unsolved for a while.

A big example of DNA evidence is the Golden State Killer. In the case of the Golden State Killer, DNA evidence was put into a genealogy database called GEDmatch (Zimmer, 2019). Police took DNA off of Joseph James DeAngelo’s trash and car door handle after obtaining a warrant (“Golden State Killer Warrants Show Evolution of Killer — but Not Genealogy,” 2018). The sample from the car door handle gave the authorities a mix of three different people. Tissue from his trash gave consistent results, that DeAngelo was extremely likely to be the Golden State Killer, also known as the East Area Rapist. According to warrants, there were 58 official case files on the killer, regarding to both sexual assault and homicide (“Golden State Killer Warrants Show Evolution of Killer — but Not Genealogy,” 2018). 58 official cases were solved using trash evidence and GEDmatch.

GEDmatch is a public website where users upload genetic data

and can search for possible relatives (Zimmer, 2019). Investigators spend months looking at family trees and finding relatives with the DNA sample (Zimmer, 2019). They eventually found DeAngelo and landed on him as their suspect. They were able to obtain the warrant to his trash to find the tissue and confirm a match (Zimmer, 2019).

The idea of using information on websites like GEDmatch raises some ethical concerns and questions. A concern is that a precedent is set when this is used in sexual assaults and cold cases, for example, homicides (Zimmer, 2019). This method could be expanded and begin to be used for petty crimes. The main concern about this situation is that when a sample is uploaded by a civilian, there is a certain idea of privacy; their DNA was likely not intended to incriminate a family member (Zimmer, 2019). When they entered the information, it was not intended for the police to be able to search for possible criminals.

Maryland State House Delegate Charles Sydnor is passionate about ethical issues using these databases. He introduced Bill HB30 (Zimmer, 2019). In Maryland, Bill HB30 prevents someone from searching statewide DNA or any genetic information databases for the objective of finding an offender with the only reason of looking for possible relatives (*Legislation - HB0030*, n.d.). This method of investigation has been used across the country after the arrest of the Golden State Killer (Zimmer, 2019). Several cold cases have been solved, leading to family and friends having significant closure. Zimmer (2019) states that due to the many cold cases that have been solved, the technology must continue to be used, and communities must support its usage, due to the benefits (Zimmer, 2019). The process has helped many families and victims get closure and justice and is necessary to continue to be used.

Chamberlain (2012) names this process “familial searching,” the main goal of this process is to find someone with similar DNA. Investigators comb through a DNA database, seeing if

they can find a match. If unsuccessful, they move onto the next (Chamberlain, 2012). One concern of using this method is that crime tends to run in families. Relatives may be reluctant to share information with investigators, given their possible connection to crimes. Additionally, people should not fall under suspicion because they have criminal relatives (Chamberlain, 2012). As of this writing, only a few states, California, Colorado, Virginia and Florida, have formal protocols for this investigative method. The District of Columbia and Maryland have prohibited use of familial searching (Chamberlain, 2012). The states have decided to not allow the process to be used to solve criminal cases.

California's protocols for familial searching requires the process to be exclusive for sexual assault and homicide cases. This process begins with a letter to a committee asking for the search to be done for a specific case (Chamberlain, 2012). The next step indicates that it must include a full 15-locus single source DNA profile that has been run through state and national DNA databases with no results (Chamberlain, 2012). This means that there is no profile for the samples to be compared to in the database of missing persons and already convicted individuals. Another aspect of criteria is how much untested DNA is left over from the crime scene to grant special testing. The last piece of the process is for the police agency and district attorney to meet and agree to move forward with familial searching (Chamberlain, 2012). Lawyers and officers have to agree to approve the need to use this process in order for it to go forward.

DNA's Impact on Investigative & Judicial Outcomes

DNA evidence has become an important aspect of forensic science and police investigations since the 1980s (Wilson et al., 2011). It has identified suspects, and exonerated people wrongfully convicted of crimes. In 2010, 255 incarcerated individuals were released, 17 from death row (Wilson et al., 2011). In 2019, one example was

Micheal Morton. Morton was wrongfully accused and prosecuted as his wife's attacker and murderer.

Micheal Morton's wife, Christine was found dead in her bed in 1986, in Texas. A jury convicted Morton of his wife's death, despite evidence supporting his innocence (McGlynn, 2019). 24 years later, he was able to receive a post-conviction DNA test and database search. Michael was able to prove his innocence. The son, who was home when his mother was murdered, claimed that his father was not home (McGlynn, 2019). A bloody bandanna was also found about 100 yards from the home. This was tested in 2010 and proved that Morton was wrongfully convicted (McGlynn, 2019). However, there is no formal procedure that allows for inmates to request DNA testing (Berger, 2006). This doesn't make it easy for people wrongfully convicted to have the opportunity to be proven innocent.

Expanding Uses of DNA & Genealogical Tools

There are some concerns of using systems like familial searching. Despite evidence of crime running in families, it does not mean someone's relative is a criminal (Chamberlain, 2012). In addition, there is an expectation of privacy with using an open database like GEDMatch. Uploading a suspect DNA may share data about biological relatives (Guest, 2019). DNA samples might contain information about an individual, and there is not a guarantee that the information is secure and protected in the database (Guest, 2019). In response to these concerns, Maryland Delegate Charles Syndor created Legislation HB30, which would not allow for a person to perform research within a statewide and public DNA database for the purpose of identifying an offender through the offender's family (Zimmer, 2019). It prohibits someone from searching the DNA databases with the sole purpose of finding a criminal's loved ones to try and convict said criminal.

The Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) is a software

program used for convicted offenders, missing people, and unsolved evidence. (*Bureau of Justice Statistics*, n.d.). CODIS is used to easily track convicted criminals and people who have gone missing. It is a useful tool in forensics. However, shed DNA has a significant fourth amendment issue. Some fear that the CODIS system markers could contain medical information (D.H. Kaye, 2004). The fear is that officers can access private information, that they have little jurisdiction to observe, along with private information being easy to find.

Legal & Ethical Considerations

The Fourth Amendment protects from unlawful and unreasonable search and seizures (Collins, 2013). The Fourth Amendment does not protect from DNA theft. DNA theft is a misdemeanor and can be punishable by up to one-year jail time and/or a \$1000 fine (Collins, 2013). Fourth amendment protections do not apply to items that have been deliberately discarded, there is no expectation of privacy on abandoned property (Collins, 2013). If a suspect were to place garbage bags onto the street, the Fourth Amendment would not protect them from unwarranted searches, as the items are considered trash (Collins, 2013). The same would apply to a cigarette butt, or a piece of gum. Items that have been thrown out have been considered to be no longer that person's property, and do not require a warrant.

An issue with DNA theft is the lack of privacy it leaves behind. It makes it difficult for information to remain private and personal. Many DNA databases screen for diseases and disorders, and with the DNA that private information is at risk (Collins, 2013). It can also open possibilities for discrimination. This information can be used by employers, health care insurance companies, and others to discriminate against people when making decisions (Collins, 2013). Some information used, like disorders, can be used against patients and suspects for discrimination. Often, people will

be discriminated against by insurance companies. (*MedlinePlus Genetics*, n.d.) If they have a gene disorder or mutation, companies may increase the cost.

When a research project is considered, informed consent is required. The subjects can decide for themselves whether to participate or not. When there is little possibility of informed consent, the researcher must decide. If it betters the general health or population, then the research project can proceed (Lazzarini et al., 2009). The same could be considered for DNA testing. DNA testing is considered the gold standard (Giannelli, 2011). However, in the beginning of DNA evidence, *People v. Castro* show some major lab errors. It also opened the question: is it fair for a conviction to happen solely on DNA evidence? (Giannelli, 2011). Convictions happen with a number of evidence being compiled together to support, can an arrest and conviction happen with only DNA to back it up.

When a rape occurred at Duke University, lawyers received a nontestimonial order for the suspected lacrosse players DNA (Giannelli, 2009). It allowed them to test the players' DNA, which would help move the case along. Even though they did it willingly, the lacrosse team's lawyers thought it to be a privacy violation (Giannelli, 2009). Nontestimonial orders are issued when there is less than complete probable cause. It needs to be proven if the suspect is related to this crime (*NC PRO*, n.d.). Taking DNA for analysis could be considered a "seizure" of the person, which would mean that the individual would be under control of the police (Giannelli, 2009). The person would be considered under police control, which is a fourth amendment violation to other people.

Societal Implications & Criminal Justice Policy

As of January 2021, there was no formal process for requesting DNA tests within prison for possibly wrongly convicted individuals (Berger, 2006). There is no process that allows for wrongfully

convicted to be freed from a sentence they do not deserve. Only 2 states, New York and Illinois, have statutes in place (Berger, 2006). In the case of Christine Morton mentioned above, her husband was convicted and only released upon DNA testing the bloody bandanna found near the home. Without this evidence, the case might have remained unsolved. (McGlynn, 2019) Using trash DNA can provide vital information for cases (Chamberlain, 2012). It can open up suspects and help solve cases that have been considered cold. It allows criminal cases to be solved faster and better.

There is significant concern about using CODIS. Some perspectives are it is a way to access private medical information (D.H. Kaye, 2004). There are also a myriad of concerns about using public DNA databases to find perpetrators, since crime can run in families but just because someone's family is a criminal, doesn't mean they are as well (Chamberlain, 2012). Just being related to a criminal does not mean that someone is guaranteed to be a criminal themselves.

Cases

In 1993, seven people were found dead in a chicken and pasta restaurant in Illinois ("How to Catch a Criminal," 2022). The only piece of compelling evidence was a piece of chicken, partially eaten. Due to the closing shift duties, all trash bins were taken out and changed. 5 victims were found in the freezer, and the remaining two were found in the walk-in cooler. All were found shot to death; some were also stabbed. No casings were left behind and there were no suspect fingerprints. The chicken was placed into a freezer for nine years ("How to Catch a Criminal: Taking a Bite Into Crime.", 2022). Cold case evidence, like the chicken, are placed into storage in case there is a break in the case.

In 2002, a woman called the police and stated that she knew what happened that night and couldn't hold onto it any longer ("How to Catch a Criminal: Taking a Bite Into Crime.," 2022).

She explained that her boyfriend, Jim Degorski, at the time called and told her to watch the news to see the big thing he did. He explained that his friend, Juan Luna, wanted to know what it was like to kill someone (“How to Catch a Criminal,” 2022). His motive for killing was curiosity. Since Luna worked at the restaurant for a while, and knew the ins and outs, they decided to do it there. Her testimony fit the description of the scene, but it was not enough to prosecute. They tested the chicken and found the two boys to be a match (“How to Catch a Criminal,” 2022). The DNA on the chicken was a match to the men, and they were able to prove that they were at the crime scene.

In February 2020, Joseph Llyod James was convicted for the first-degree murder of Phyllis Hunhoff. In 2018, James took control of her car, and drove from Utica, South Dakota to Norfolk, Nebraska. The next morning, James strangled and stabbed Phyllis. She died within her vehicle (“How to Catch a Criminal: Taking a Bite Into Crime.,” 2022). He then drove her car to a gas station, filled up her tank, then took the car to a wooded area. He burned the car with Phyllis’s body inside. He threw away the T-shirt he was wearing during the crime, which investigators recovered (“How to Catch a Criminal: Taking a Bite Into Crime.,” 2022). Both Phyllis’s and James’s blood were on the shirt. The item he deemed trash was critical to solving the case.

On March 28, 2023, a man was arrested for a firebombing in 2022. A number of DNA was collected (*Department of Justice Documents*, 2022). Then officers noticed a man, Hridindu Sankar Roychowdhury, was identified as a possible suspect and monitored. They noticed him throwing food and throwing items away (“Wisconsin Man Charged With Firebombing Building,” 2022). The trash was collected and tested against the crime scene DNA and proved him to be the culprit (“Wisconsin Man Charged With Firebombing Building,” 2022). The trash Roychowdhury threw away proved to be the thing to convict him.

In July 2018, Eric Cain thought he was getting pulled over but the men in the police uniforms were not officers (Webb, 2020). The faux police officers handcuffed Cain and tortured him for several hours before he managed to escape (Webb, 2020). After the incident was reported, the house Cain was taken to was searched. A cigarette butt was found and taken for DNA analysis. The CODIS search showed the perpetrator to be Kenneth Hicks (Webb, 2020). They searched the system and found that Hicks' DNA was a match. He was taken into custody. He asked for coffee and cigarettes, and when told they found his DNA at the house, he asked for a lawyer (Webb, 2020). He exercised his right to be a lawyer.

Hicks continued to ask for cigarettes while being taken to processing (Webb, 2020). The officers gave Hicks the cigarettes requested and waited outside the building while he smoked them. He then threw one of the cigarettes to the ground and said, "here's your DNA" (Webb, 2020). They collected the sample and tested it without a warrant. The DNA was a match and Cain was arrested (Webb, 2020). Cain sought to have the evidence thrown away since it was obtained without a warrant. The courts said, "[A] person who voluntarily abandons property in the absence of an unconstitutional seizure has no legitimate expectation of privacy in it, and therefore its search or seizure does not violate his Fourth Amendment rights" (Webb, 2020, pg.4-5). The item was considered trash and no longer valuable to the person, so there is a right of privacy for it.

Gaps in Research and Recommendations

There are a myriad of gaps in research. It was a struggle to find cases where trash from DNA was used. There was very little research on the topic, and a number of the research led me down different roads to trash DNA. There also did not seem to be an exact phrase for this topic. Most sources, like the Kenneth Hicks

case above, argued about the Fourth Amendment violations. The limited scholarly attention to trash DNA as a discrete investigative method highlights a significant gap in forensic policy research, particularly regarding standardized procedures, ethical oversight, and constitutional analysis.

I would recommend establishing statutory standards for garbage collection DNA. I would recommend more research into the system Dewey-Hagborg created to process DNA samples. I recommend using the program and possibly improving it, so it is more accurate to find missing people and help solve criminal investigations. Further, I recommend further research on the Fourth Amendment considerations surrounding the procedure. Using trash DNA, or abandoned samples, may prove very vital to the criminal justice system if used responsibly and carefully. I would, in addition, recommend more research overall on the general topic, done by lawyers and fellow members of the criminal justice system. Knowing the ethical limits is important.

CONCLUSION

Trashed, or abandoned samples in criminal investigations, hold a major ethical concern. The question of exact use requires further investigation and Fourth Amendment rights considerations. This can be dangerous if the ethical concerns are not understood. Using DNA from trash can be possibly abused and it is important to give it limitations and research the topic. This technology is already being used and could possibly become dangerous if not researched further. DNA theft and misuse by the criminal justice system are among the biggest threats.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would first like to thank my amazing mentor, Dr. Darian Senn-Carter, for the wonderful support, as well for creating an environment for questions and concerns. Without his support and

guidance, I would be lost. I would like to thank my family and the Super Science Club for their support and love; and listening to me talk about it for many hours. A huge thanks to Effie Gentry for bringing the original NPR article and helping formulate the idea, and the biggest thanks to Alex Bradford for convincing me to apply to Anne Arundel Community College. Without those two, a lot of this wouldn't have happened.

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